

Food safety and to them adverse events caused by certain nutritional supplements being added

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Annotation: This article discusses the safety of food and the rules of use of food additives and the negative consequences of its use.

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Introduction

In a country where the quality of imported goods is controlled using high technology on the basis of scientific advances, the country imports a large number of competitive quality goods. The markets of countries where certification and quality control of goods are carried out by backward methods are dominated by a large number of low-quality imported goods [1-3].

The peculiarity of the assessment of supply and demand for food products is that from time immemorial, food in the market has been valued at low prices. In a market where the consumer has a choice, there will be an impact of factors other than just the price of the product.

The amount of minerals in some foods is also an indicator of their quality. For example, the more minerals in wheat flour, the lower its quality. In quality management, it is possible to evaluate products on only one indicator. For example, the quality of ascorbic acid in poultry, poultry meat, the amount of tertiary acids in beverages, the taste, smell and color of juices are evaluated [4-7].

From this information, the consumer can find the caloric value of the product, its value in terms of dietary and nutritional value, chemical composition,

It is based on organoleptic and chemical methods of inspection, which are currently used in practice in our country in accordance with state standards and specifications for food products. Certification of products in accordance with the requirements of international standards requires reliance on advanced modern

methods of inspection. A number of methods used by state standards today cause a number of problems due to the fact that the quality description of food products, which are obsolete and not fully scientifically based, does not fully reflect the current level of development of technologies in their preparation [8-11]. Synthetic preservatives, synthetic dyes used for food, flavorings and sweeteners used to improve the appearance of the brand. focusing on the absence of. Because every year thousands of new synthesized products appear in the markets. However, the risk of poisoning from synthetic chemicals is not well understood.

The expansion of international economic relations of our country, the increase in the volume of movement of goods and the emergence of new problems related to quality and composition require the existence of many pressing issues and their immediate solution. The solution of this problem will be the basis for the creation of state standards and specifications based on new advanced methods of inspection on the basis of modern technologies [12].

Inadequate methods of conducting food examinations in the activities of certification bodies, testing laboratories and customs examinations often lead to the mere study of the "passport" of the product. Passports do not always guarantee quality [13-15].

Therefore, one of the most pressing issues in this area today is the need to develop new operational methods of verification of applicable state standards and specifications for food products and to introduce appropriate science-based additives.

Imported, as well as domestically produced soft drinks are mainly based on the preparation of feed additives. The fact that the climate of the republic is hot and the duration of the summer is a bit longer also increases the demand of the population for thirst-quenching drinks [16]. Taking advantage of such high demand and supply in the market, some counterfeiters try to import products that are unsuitable for consumption in various ways, ie in excess of synthetic preservatives and synthetic dyes that ensure the long-term storage of the drink. Such products imported to our country do not meet the standards of the country of origin. The issuance of certificates of conformity by certification bodies is limited to the detection of heavy metals as the main criterion for their safety and quality [17].

According to the World Health Organization, 4 (four) million people worldwide die each year. one person died of cancer. Another 6 (six) million per year. one person becomes ill with this disease. 35% of these people suffer from chronic malnutrition due to poor nutrition, ie consumption of products containing various synthetic preservatives, synthetic coloring dyes and other nutrients [18].

Our country is one of the largest consumers of soft drinks. In other words, on average, 12,498 tons of soft drinks and food additives, including fruit juices, are imported annually in the amount of 11,861 thousand US dollars. It is safe to say that more than 35% of cancer patients in the country suffer from malnutrition.

It is known that the quality of food products, including soft drinks, in accordance with the requirements of the Republican Standard Oz DST 991: 2001, only physicochemical parameters of carbon dioxide and alcohol content meet the specified standards (p.1.2.6.), the most characteristic use of beverages, carbonic

acids, flavorings, preservatives, natural and synthetic dyes that are safe for human health, the use of which is the most characteristic for beverages, the quantitative norms allowed for beverage production are not specified [20-22].

Clause 1.2.10 states that the difference in the permissible weight, acidity, density, moisture content of the dry matter on the physicochemical parameters of beverages meets the specified requirements, and the permissible norms of these parameters are not set in beverages.

In paragraph 3.3.9 of DST 925: 2004 only toxic elements: lead, arsenic, cadmium, mercury, copper, zinc; radionuclides: cesium-237, strontium-90 and caffeine are not allowed to exceed the specified level, the main physicochemical parameters that determine the quality of the drink are the permitted nutrients, the specified quantitative standards of coloring synthetic dyes are not specified.

Paragraph 1.8.5 of the Sanitary and Epidemiological Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan SanQM (SanPiN) 0138-03 of the Regulation of Food Safety also contains only the permissible levels of the above toxic elements.

The section of this document, which provides information on the normative indicators of the use of food additives and coloring additives, contains only a list of permitted food additives. However, the permissible quantitative norms for the addition of these compounds and coloring dyes to the product are not specified.

It is known that any change that occurs in fatty foods, including soft drinks, fruit juices, affects their taste, smell and color, the taste of the product becomes bitter and creates a peculiar unpleasant odor. The foaming of fat in food is caused by the enzyme lipase, which passes through the tissues of animals and plants or bacteria, especially the cells of the pancreas [23].

The fatty acids released during the foaming process give the oil a foreign taste and odor characteristic of these substances. Therefore, it is very important to check the acidity level for vegetable oils and animal fats used in food, which is a key indicator in determining its quality. The acidity level is the mass (mg) of potassium hydroxide (KOH) used to neutralize the free fatty acids in 1 g of fat. This amount is 0.4-2.25 mg in vegetable oil, 2.0 mg in margarine, 1.5 mg in animal fats, 1.3-4.0 mg in sunflower oil (Speransky V.G., Inikhov G.S., Montitsky R.I., Soboleva M.I., 1965; Skurixin I.M., Nechaev A.P. 1998; Nechaev A.P. 2004).

Excessive levels of free fatty acids in the products spoil the quality of this product. Various antioxidants, preservatives and coloring synthetic dyes are used to prevent the hydrolysis of lipids in food and the formation of free fatty acids, reduce volatile acids, prevent microbiological growth.

For example, in the preparation of poultry meat, technological processing has been improved, as a result of processing of poultry patina by boiling water before cleaning, fatty acids in the form of short-length molecules are formed in its body and naturally increase the acidity of the product [24]. However, the quality of this product is recognized through inspections on current standard indicators. There is reason to be skeptical of these results. Based on this objection, it can be said that the addition of large amounts of antioxidants to the diet of chickens before delivery to the kitchen leads to a decrease in GOST.

Antioxidants are harmless to humans when present in small amounts. Due to the presence of antioxidants in a healthy cell of the human body, their division is maintained at a stationary level. The presence of large amounts of antioxidants leads to the expression of oncogenes, which in turn causes the benign tumor to turn into a malignant tumor [25].

According to data provided by the Joint Board of Experts on Nutritional Supplements (FAO / WHO), a range of antioxidants that are difficult to detect is 25 mg/kg (butylhydroxytoluene relative to body weight, or ionol (E 321), butylhydroxyanisole (E 320), vitamin E-tocopherols (E 306, E 307, E 308, E 309). Examination of the effect of antioxidants on the organism of experimental animals shows that they have a hepatocarcinogenic effect (development of malignant tumors in the liver). . WHO, Geneva, 1999)

The Joint Board of Experts on Nutritional Supplements (FAO / WHO) has strictly stated that the daily dose of certain permitted antioxidants should not exceed 0.5 mg per 1 kg of human body. The use of the antioxidant Gvayakovaya smala (E 314) in food is banned in a number of European countries, as well as in Russia [26].

The results of scientific research are based on experiments and many years of observations of some antioxidants, preservatives tin chloride (E 512), formaldehyde (E 240), AF-2 - nitrofurans, thiabendazole (E 233), coloring synthetic dyes based on red, methyl red, from water 4, methyl orange, Congo red, alizarin red V, eriochrome, blue tryptophan, blue evansa, consumable blue S (E 142) and puntsovyx SX (E 125) exhibit mutagenic properties in the body.

Methyl yellow from the dyes, orange 11 and phloxindar exhibit mutagenic properties in the cell of plants. Animal experiments have shown that the dye colorant (E 150a and E 150s) can cause chromosome mutations. Coloring dyes such as tatzine (E 102), indigo carmine (E 132), sunset yellow ("sunny zakat" FCF, E 110), azorubin (E 122) and patented V (E 131) were found to be mutagenic in lymphocytes in the blood in experiments on mice. (Golubev V.N., Chicheva-Filatova L.V., Shlenskaya T.V. 2003; Popovich N.A., Kataeva S.E., Melnichenko T.I. 2004).

The use of yellow-red amaranth dye for food coloring has been banned since 1971 (Skurikhin I.M., Nechaev A.P. 1991; Nechaev A.P. 2004.).

In a number of experiments with animals, it became clear that these compounds lead to the formation of dangerous tumors.

The main requirement for food coloring compounds is their safety for the human body. For example, sulfur dioxide SO_2 , H_2SO_3 solution and its salts have bleaching and preservative properties, such as SO_2 melanoids. At the same time SO_2 breaks down vitamin B₁, affects the protein molecule, and this leads to negative consequences in the body.

Nitrite and nitrate potassium are used to preserve the red color of meat and meat products (salting).

Myoglobin-red coloring agent, when combined with nitrites, forms nitrosomyoglobin, which gives red salted meat color, which does not change when meat is boiled. Potassium nitrite, which is converted to potassium nitrate by enzymes secreted by microorganisms, has a similar effect. Currently, the use of nitrite and

nitrate is causing complaints from medical professionals and this requires further study.

Bromate potassium $KBrO_3$ is used to whiten flour products, however, its use leads to the breakdown of vitamins B_1 , PP, and methionine.

According to toxicological studies in rats, a decrease in hemoglobin levels was observed as a result of the ingestion of tartrazine at 42.2 mg / kg body weight into rats. A dose of 5.3 mg / kg body weight of indigocarmine caused a toxic effect in rats when given for 10 months. Erythrosine has been shown to adversely affect the pituitary-thyroid system. (Popovich N.A., Kataeva S.E., Melnichenko T.I. 2004).

The production of soft drinks in the country is based on the use of synthetic, ie artificial flavoring and coloring chemical feed additives. No production quantification methods have been developed to determine their safety for consumption in production. The issuance of certificates of conformity by certification bodies is limited to the detection of heavy metals as the main criterion for their safety and quality.

The high incidence of liver disease and diseases of the digestive system in children is likely to be due to the fact that, based on the above information, they consumed beverages with an unspecified concentration of coloring compounds. Based on the above information, knowing and applying the permissible norms in the use of nutrient supplements is one of the most pressing issues.

References

1. Холдаров Д. М., Шодиев Д. А., Райимбердиева Г. Г. Геохимия микроэлементов в элементарных ландшафтах пустынной зоны //Актуальные проблемы современной науки. – 2018. – №. 3. – С. 77-81.
2. Шодиев Д. А., Нажмитдинова Г. К. Пищевые добавки и их значение //Universum: технические науки. – 2021. – №. 10-3 (91). – С. 30-32.
3. Шодиев Д. А. У., Нажмитдинова Г. К. К. А. Специфические аспекты производства продуктов питания //Universum: технические науки. – 2021. – №. 3-2 (84). – С. 91-94.
4. Guljakhon N. THE ROLE OF THE STEVIA PLANT IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY //Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences. – 2021. – С. 334-338.
5. Ergashev A. A., Najmitdinova G. K. Features of differentiated teaching of chemistry //Экономика и социум. – 2020. – №. 12-1. – С. 89-92.
6. Sattarova B., Shodiev D., Haqiqatkhon D. The determination of the composition and structure of ferrocenyl benzoic acids by mass spectrometric and potentiometric

- methods //Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 56-58.
7. Sattarova B., Farangiz I. Effects of ice cream concentration with cocoa on human health //Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 01. – С. 86-91.
8. Sattarova B. N., Maxmudova A. A. MEVA-REZAVOR QANDOLAT MAHSULOTLARI //Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects. – 2022. – С. 112-116.
9. Sattarova B., Mokhlaroyim K. Extraction of oil by pressing //Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 02. – С. 8-13.
10. Sattarova B., Farangiz I. QUALITY INDICATORS OF FLAVORINGS ADDED TO ICE CREAM //Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 02. – С. 20-25.
11. Shodiev D., Haqiqatkhon D., Zulaykho A. Useful properties of the amaranth plant //ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 55-58.
12. Алиева Ф. А. К., Шодиев Д. А. У., Далимова Х. Х. К. УФ-видимый записывающий спектрофотометр уф-2201 спектрофотометр исследование синтетических красителей в безалкогольных напитках //Universum: технические науки. – 2021. – №. 11-3 (92). – С. 66-69.
13. Shodiev D., Hojjali Q. Medicinal properties of amaranth oil in the food industry //Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences. – 2021. – С. 205-208.
14. Шодиев Д. А. У., Расулова У. Н. К. ЗНАЧЕНИЕ АМАРАНТОВОГО МАСЛА В МЕДИЦИНЕ //Universum: технические науки. – 2022. – №. 1-2 (94). – С. 69-72.
15. Kholdarov D. et al. ON GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS AND MECHANICAL COMPOSITION OF SALINE MEADOW SAZ SOILS //Конференции. – 2021.
16. (84)), 91-94. Najmitdinova G. USEFUL PROPERTIES OF NATURAL DRY MILK //International Journal of Advance Scientific Research. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 04. – С. 43-50.
17. Саттарова Б. Н., Аскарлов И. Р., Джураев А. М. Некоторые вопросы классификации куриного мяса //Universum: химия и биология. – 2018. – №. 11 (53). – С. 36-38.

18. Саттарова Б. Н. и др. Влияние полученных биостимуляторов на повышение живой массы цыплят //Universum: химия и биология. – 2019. – №. 12 (66).
19. Саттарова Б. Н., Омонов Н. О. Ё., Уринов Х. К. У. Определение антиоксидантов в местном курином мясе на хромато-масс-спектрометре //Universum: технические науки. – 2021. – №. 5-5 (86). – С. 6-8.
20. Sattarova B., Mokhlaroyim K. Extraction of oil by pressing //Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 02. – С. 8-13.
21. Sattarova B., Saidmakhammadjon J. FACTORS AFFECTING THE QUALITY OF VEGETABLE PRODUCTS AND CANNED VEGETABLES //Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 02. – С. 14-19.
22. Sattarova B., Alieva F. EQUIPMENT FOR CAPILLARY ELECTROPHORESIS (CEF) FOR THE PRODUCTION OF SOFT DRINKS IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY CONTROL METHOD USING //Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 01. – С. 47-51.
23. Алиева Ф. А. К., Шодиев Д. А. У., Далимова Х. Х. К. УФ-видимый записывающий спектрофотометр уф-2201 спектрофотометр исследование синтетических красителей в безалкогольных напитках //Universum: технические науки. – 2021. – №. 11-3 (92). – С. 66-69.
24. Sattarova B., Xurshid A. METHODS OF CLEANING MICELLES IN THE PRODUCTION OF VEGETABLE OILS //Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences. – 2021. – С. 293-296.
25. Alieva F. SCIENTIFIC FOUNDATION OF PRODUCING TECHNOLOGY OF NON-ALCOHOLIC DRINKS //Interdisciplinary Conference of Young Scholars in Social Sciences. – 2021. – С. 330-333.
26. Alieva F., Namunakhon A. CURRENT ISSUES OF PRODUCT CERTIFICATION AT THE INTERNATIONAL LEVEL //Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects. – 2022. – С. 86-90.

